

ODDEA Working paper

Mitigating the Digital Divide: Exploring moderation and mediation effects on E-Health performance in a comparative study of Europe and Southeast Asia

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Abstract

The digital divide significantly influences healthcare accessibility and outcomes, particularly in the context of eHealth technologies. Disparities in eHealth adoption between Europe and Southeast Asia highlight the impact of E-government development on eHealth performance, focusing on digital literacy as a mediating factor and religious beliefs as a moderating variable. A quantitative analysis utilized secondary data from 31 geographically diverse countries, representing both developed and emerging economies, spanning 2019 to 2022. This period was selected as the COVID-19 pandemic intensified the digital divide in eHealth adoption and accessibility. The results indicate that E-government development positively influences eHealth performance, with digital literacy significantly mediating this relationship. Additionally, religious beliefs, particularly Atheism, moderate the relationship between E-government development and eHealth performance, suggesting that regions with lower religiosity are more receptive to eHealth technologies. The findings underscore the importance of integrating digital literacy initiatives alongside E-government development to enhance eHealth performance. Policymakers should consider the cultural and religious landscape when designing eHealth strategies to ensure equitable access to healthcare resources.

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